

From the establishment of a national bioinformatics society to the development of a national bioinformatics infrastructure

Data federation advocacy attempts

Towards a centralized repository for COVID-19 Data

The European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL EBI) took the lead in developing the <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/> (Harrison et al., 2021) with the aim of establishing a centralized platform for accessing, analyzing, and sharing data concerning the COVID-19 pandemic. Following the establishment of the central instance, national instances have been rolled out in various European countries since 2022. Of note, the COVID-19 Data Portal was characterized by an increased data usability (Sheehan et al., 2023) when compared to alternative data submission structures.

The funding and research representatives from European countries were asked to help motivate research and medical groups to submit the data to the COVID-19 Data Portal. Although research groups benefiting from public funding were urged to submit generated data to public repositories, there were no specific mandates regarding the type of data to be submitted or the specific repositories where it should be deposited.

RSBI was nominated to join this pan-European initiative and help data submission nationwide. RSBI's strategy involved emphasizing to research groups the significance of data submission, underscoring the heightened accessibility and enriched insights stemming from enhanced metadata. To help with the technical aspects of data submission, RSBI facilitated meetings between experts on ENA and Galaxy from EMBL-EBI and ELIXIR National Nodes and Romanian research groups. Concurrently, RSBI advocated to representatives of the Romanian Ministry of Research, Innovation, and Digitalization the necessity of enforcing proper data submission protocols for research funded by public sources, and the opportunity to develop national pathogen data portals with technical support within the COVID-19 Data Portal project.

Despite the effort, the national data submissions were limited (85 viral isolates sequenced in Romania being available on the COVID-19 Data Portal). We posit that the main factors explaining the low submissions are: lack of human resources with data management and submission experience, lack of a national strategy concerning molecular data and notably the lack of a pathogen data portal.

Federated EGA data efforts

As part of the "Bioinformatics Capacity Building- Human Genomics" bilateral project with ELIXIR Norway, RSBI addressed the challenges of federating human 'omics data. To this purpose, several medical genetics groups generating such data convened to address federation issues in a meeting held in Timisoara in 2022, followed by subsequent online discussions. The primary focus was on identifying how the technical approaches for data federation practiced in several ELIXIR countries could be adapted in Romania.

An important outcome was a shared understanding of the necessity to share data, the technical complexities involved in managing central data repository, and the role of Data Access Committees. The discussions followed the Maturity Model FEGA (<https://inab.github.io/feqa-mm/>) and were facilitated by representatives from ELIXIR Norway.

These discussions also provided valuable insights that helped craft a well-informed message for communication with the government, likely contributing to its commitment towards the European data federation, and the signing of the "1 Million Genomes" Declaration in 2023.

Harrison, P.W., Lopez, R., Rahman, N., Allen, S.G., Aslam, R., Buso, N., Cummins, C., Fathy, Y., Felix, E., Glont, M., Jayathilaka, S., Kadam, S., Kumar, M., Lauer, K.B., Malhotra, G., Mosaku, A., Edbali, O., Park, Y.M., Parton, A., Pearce, M., Estrada Pena, J.F., Rossetto, J., Russell, C., Selvakumar, S., Sitjà, X.P., Sokolov, A., Thorne, R., Ventouratou, M., Walter, P., Yordanova, G., Zadissa, A., Cochrane, G., Blomberg, N., Apweiler, R., 2021. The COVID-19 Data Portal: accelerating SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 research through rapid open access data sharing. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 49, W619–W623. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab417>

Sheehan, N., Leonelli, S., Botta, F., 2023. From Collection to Analysis: A Comparison of GISAID and the Covid-19 Data Portal. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.05.13.540634>